

Interviewed participants demographics data

	School	Teaching experience (years)	Teaching subject	Gender
Participant #1	#1	7	Science	Female
Participant #2	#1	7	Technology	Male
Participant #3	#1	5	Arts/Music	Female
Participant #4	#2	27	Social science	Male
Participant #5	#2	23	Arts/Music	Female
Participant #6	#2	25	Mathematics	Female
Participant #7	#2	19	Science	Female